

ЕНЕРГИЕН ФОРУМ 2018

ОЦЕНКА НА МАТЕРИАЛНАТА БАРИЕРА ПРЕД РАЗПРОСТРАНЕНИЕТО НА РЕАКТОРЕН ПЛУТОНИЙ В КРАЯ НА ГОРИВНАТА КАМПАНИЯ

Ивайло Найденов, Калин Филипов

ASSESSMENT OF REACTOR-GRADE PLUTONIUM PROLIFERATION BARRIER AT FUEL DISCHARGE

Ivaylo Naydenov, Kalin Filipov

В настоящата статия са представени резултати от извършена оценка на качествата на материалната бариера на плутоний, получен в референтен реактор с вода под налягане при експлоатацията на референтно ураново и уран-плутониево гориво. Разгледан е изотопният състав на плутония в момента на спиране на реактора като не се разглежда изменението му, породено от престоя на отработеното гориво в активната зона на реактора до момента на извеждането му, както и при отлежаването, транспорта и други операции с горивото. Оценката е извършена по две независими методики, като резултатите са сравнени и е налице ясна сходимост между тях.

Non-proliferation and proliferation barriers

Nuclear materials' non-proliferation is defined by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) as a property of a nuclear system or facility that impedes nuclear material's diversion and/or undeclared production, as well as malicious applications of nuclear technology by a state aiming to acquire nuclear weapon or other type of nuclear explosive device. That definition implies that proliferation resistance is a measure of the difficulties that should be overcome in order to develop and/or acquire nuclear weapon or nuclear explosive device by means of civilian fuel cycle and civilian technologies. Those difficulties include but are not limited to technical and technological barriers, required skills, time, etc. Misusing nuclear fuel cycle could include usage of materials, equipment, technological processes,

facilities, and knowledge related to civilian fuel cycle [1]. In the case of nuclear proliferation the misuse of nuclear material and/or nuclear facilities is carried out by the owning country [2]. In order to define the level of civilian plutonium's usability for nuclear explosive device construction, it is necessary to analyse those properties of the material that could make it suitable for non-civilian applications. Most often, the attributes linked to material's proliferation resistance are the bare critical mass of a sphere, its decay heat, the spontaneous neutron emission, and the radiological barrier [3,4].

Methodologies

The 'Figure of Merit' methodology has been developed by a team from USA's Los Alamos National Laboratories. It is used to assess the material's usability for the construction of a nuclear explosive device by a nation or a sub-national group. The methodology uses two criteria, FOM_1 and FOM_2 , in order to assess the material. They are calculated using Eqs. (1) and (2). These criteria include several intrinsic factors such as bare critical mass, spontaneous neutron fraction, decay heat, and dose rate:

$$FOM_1 = 1 - \lg \left[\frac{M}{800} + \frac{M \cdot DH}{4500} + \frac{M}{50} \left(\frac{DR}{500} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] \quad (1)$$

$$FOM_2 = 1 - \lg \left[\frac{M}{800} + \frac{M \cdot DH}{4500} + \frac{M \cdot S}{6.8 \cdot 10^6} + \frac{M}{50} \left(\frac{DR}{500} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] \quad (2)$$

In Eqs. (1) and (2) M is the bare critical mass of a sphere in kg, DH is the specific decay heat in $W \cdot kg^{-1}$, S is the spontaneous neutron fraction in $(n \cdot s^{-1}) \cdot kg^{-1}$, and DR is the dose rate of 20% of the bare critical mass at a distance of 1 m from the source in $rad \cdot h^{-1}$. The higher the criteria value, the higher the material's usability [2,5,6].

The multi-attribute utility analysis (MAUA) has been developed by Charlton et al. as a means to assess the nuclear security (including both proliferation resistance and physical protection aspects) of nuclear processes. The analysis evaluates 14 utility functions, linked to proliferation barriers. The sum of the products of the relative weights and utility functions' values is used as a metric named 'static proliferation resistance' and is

calculated using Eq. (3); the sum value belongs to the interval [0;1]. The closer the value is to unity, the better is the quality of the barrier [7]. This metric is applied in the present analysis in a similar fashion as the 'Figure of Merit' criteria – as a means to evaluate the change in the material barrier's quality.

$$PR_i = \sum_{j=1}^J w_j \cdot u_j(x_{ij}) \quad (3)$$

In Eq. (3) w_j is the relative weight of the j -th utility function, $u_j(x_{ij})$ is the value of the j -th utility function for the i -th stage of the nuclear process, PR_i is the static proliferation resistance.

Assessment input data

The assessment is carried out for a reference pressurised water reactor with parameters shown in Table 1. The reference uranium-plutonium MOX fuel has been fabricated using plutonium, extracted from spent PWR fuel with burn-up of 45,000 MWd/tHM and cooled down for 10 years. Its isotopic composition is shown on Figure 1. The MOX fuel contains as well depleted uranium with ^{235}U assay 0.3 w%.

Table 1. Input parameters of the analysed reference PWR

Parameter	Unit of measure	Value
Gross electric power	MW	1,000.00
Gross thermodynamic efficiency of the power unit	%	32.60
Load factor of the power unit	%	85.00
Enrichment of uranium fuel	%	4.40
Plutonium weight share in MOX fuel	%	7.23

Figure 1. Isotopic vector of the plutonium, used for fresh MOX fuel fabrication [8]

The proliferation resistance criteria are assessed for both uranium (UOX) and MOX fuel as a function of burn-up. The burn-up range between 30,000 and 50,000 MWd/tHM has been selected. For the purpose of the assessment it is assumed that the plutonium is extracted immediately from the spent fuel and that the material is separated in metallic form. The isotopic compositions (vectors) have been calculated using SCALE6.1, module ORIGEN-ARP and the bare critical masses – by using SCALE6.1, module KENO V.a. [9]. The decay heat, spontaneous neutron fractions and dose rates of the plutonium mixtures have been calculated in the simplified manner applied in [10].

Results

The results of the calculations are presented in the following tables. Table 2 and Table 3 represent the isotopic compositions of plutonium, extracted from the respective type of spent fuel at discharge. Table 4 summarizes some important plutonium characteristics, linked to proliferation resistance – the bare critical masses (BCM) and decay heat (DH) of the isotopic mixtures. Table 5 shows the calculated values of different proliferation resistance criteria.

Table 2. Isotopic compositions of plutonium, extracted from spent UOX fuel as a function of burn-up

	30,000	35,000	40,000	45,000	50,000
	<i>MWd/tHM</i>	<i>MWd/tHM</i>	<i>MWd/tHM</i>	<i>MWd/tHM</i>	<i>MWd/tHM</i>
pu238	0.994%	1.298%	1.634%	1.994%	2.370%
pu239	63.058%	59.460%	56.337%	53.626%	51.271%
pu240	18.333%	19.230%	19.953%	20.546%	21.030%
pu241	14.338%	15.660%	16.593%	17.195%	17.535%
pu242	3.277%	4.352%	5.482%	6.639%	7.795%

Table 3. Isotopic compositions of plutonium, extracted from spent MOX fuel as a function of burn-up

	30,000	35,000	40,000	45,000	50,000
	<i>MWd/tHM</i>	<i>MWd/tHM</i>	<i>MWd/tHM</i>	<i>MWd/tHM</i>	<i>MWd/tHM</i>
pu238	1.368%	1.370%	1.372%	1.376%	1.381%
pu239	46.930%	45.138%	43.500%	42.039%	40.734%
pu240	27.689%	28.211%	28.610%	28.874%	29.041%
pu241	16.334%	17.049%	17.693%	18.256%	18.724%
pu242	7.679%	8.232%	8.824%	9.455%	10.119%

Table 4. Bare critical masses and decay heat of the plutonium mixtures

	UOX		MOX	
	BCM	DH	BCM	DH
<i>MWd/tHM</i>	<i>kg</i>	<i>W/kg</i>	<i>kg</i>	<i>W/kg</i>
30,000	12.726	8.616	14.831	11.127
35,000	13.086	10.371	15.229	11.170
40,000	13.602	12.282	15.310	11.210
45,000	13.714	14.312	15.721	11.246
50,000	13.827	16.420	15.758	11.280

Table 5. Values of proliferation resistance criteria for different plutonium isotopic mixtures

	FOM ₁	FOM ₂	PR
UOX 30	2.3950	1.3398	0.6812
UOX 35	2.3324	1.2787	0.6859
UOX 40	2.2666	1.2185	0.6915
UOX 45	2.2164	1.1762	0.7075
UOX 50	2.1692	1.1381	0.7131
MOX 30	2.2580	1.0505	0.6682
MOX 35	2.2454	1.0241	0.6690
MOX 40	2.2420	1.0079	0.6704
MOX 45	2.2296	0.9834	0.6716
MOX 50	2.2277	0.9702	0.6728

Figure 2. Comparison of the results obtained using 'Figure of Merit' methodology (FOM₁) and the Multi-attribute analysis (PR)

Discussion and conclusion

The results obtained by applying both methodologies suggest that plutonium's proliferation resistance strengthens with burn-up increase in the case of uranium fuel. In the case of MOX fuel, the proliferation properties of plutonium change little with burn-up increase. These effects are mainly due to the circumstance that plutonium's isotopic composition changes markedly with uranium fuel's increasing burn-up unlike the MOX fuel case.

When a comparison of the results obtained using 'Figure of Merit' methodology and multi-attribute analysis, a very good convergence is observed. That leads to the conclusion that both independent methodologies are applicable for credible proliferation resistance properties analysis and can be used for benchmarking, taking into account the limits of their application.

As a conclusion, it could be stated that increased burn-up improves reactor-grade plutonium's proliferation resistance which in turn contributes positively to the feasibility of increased burn-up of uranium fuel. On the other hand, although the proliferation criteria values remain almost unchanged in the case of MOX fuel, plutonium recycling in PWR deteriorates its isotopic composition (the relative weight share of odd fissile isotopes is lower compared to plutonium, generated by uranium fuel operation) and increases plutonium isotopic mixtures' bare critical masses and decay heat. These effects have a positive impact in terms of proliferation resistance properties.

The convergence of the criteria values of both applied methodologies shows that these methodologies may be used to assess the proliferation resistance properties of nuclear materials and provide credible benchmark.

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Authors:

Ivaylo Toshkov Naydenov, PhD, Assistant Professor, Department of Thermal and Nuclear Power Engineering, Technical University of Sofia, +359 898 597194, ivaylo.naydenov@gmail.com

Kalin Boyanov Filipov, PhD, Associated Professor, Department of Thermal and Nuclear Power Engineering, Technical University of Sofia, +359 (2) 965 2297, filipov@tu-sofia.bg